

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Unlocking C=N Bond Formation Through Microwave-Assisted Reductive Coupling of Nitroarene with Alcohols on Fe₁-N₄ Single-Atom Catalyst

Arun D. Kute¹ | Hanumant B. Kale¹ | Rohit P. Upadhyay¹ | Rostislav Langer² | Michal Otyepka^{2,3} | Shan Jiang⁴ | Jeffrey T. Miller⁴ | Yifeng Wang⁵

¹Institute of Chemical Technology, Mumbai, Marathwada Campus, Jalna, Maharashtra, India | ²IT4Innovations, VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic | ³Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, The Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN), Palacký University Olomouc, Olomouc, Czech Republic | ⁴Davidson School of Chemical Engineering, Purdue University, West Lafayette, Indiana, USA | ⁵Department of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Shandong University, Shandong, P. R. China | ⁶Nanotechnology Centre, Centre for Energy and Environmental Technologies, VŠB–Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

Correspondence: Yifeng Wang (yifeng@sdu.edu.cn) | Manoj B. Gawande (mb.gawande@marj.ictmumbai.edu.in)

Received: 6 October 2025 | **Revised:** 5 December 2025 | **Accepted:** 19 December 2025

Keywords: Fe single-atom | imination reaction | microwave | reductive coupling | solvent-free

ABSTRACT

One of the most reliable strategies in organic synthesis is the formation of C=N bonds through the reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols to produce selectively functionalized imines; however, achieving this transformation remains challenging because of the facile over-hydrogenation of the C=N bond and the low catalytic efficiency of reported systems. Herein, we report the synthesis of a highly active iron single-atom catalyst supported on N-doped graphene (Fe₁@NG) via ion adsorption and microwave irradiation. The Fe₁@NG catalyst exhibits superior performance, achieving high turnover frequency (TOF, ≈150 h⁻¹) under base- and solvent-free conditions with excellent selectivity. Characterization by HAADF-STEM, XANES, and FT-XAFS confirms atomically dispersed Fe sites coordinated to four nitrogen atoms (Fe₁-N₄) with Fe⁺³ oxidation state. Experimental and theoretical analyses reveal that the electronic structure of Fe₁-N₄ centers facilitates hydrogen borrowing, enhancing catalytic activity. The DFT study showed that on the Fe₁-N₄ catalyst, benzyl alcohol is oxidized while 4-nitrophenol is reduced to 4-aminophenol, which then couples with benzaldehyde to form the imine product. This synergy of single-atom metal sites and stabilizing π-π interactions facilitates favorable adsorption and alignment of the aromatic reactants on the conjugated support, thereby modulating reaction thermodynamics and promoting efficient imine formation. The catalyst demonstrates broad substrate compatibility (over 20 examples), scalability, and excellent stability over multiple cycles without significant loss of activity. This work presents a robust Fe-based catalyst for efficient and sustainable C—N bond formation.

1 | Introduction

The electrophilic nature of the C=N bond in imines finds broad applications in organic transformations, including reduction, addition, cyclization, and aziridination reactions [1, 2]. Therefore, imines, which possess a valuable C=N bond, serve as crucial organic intermediates in the synthesis of biologically active compounds, pharmaceuticals, agricultural chemicals, and

fine chemicals [3]. Conventionally, imines are typically synthesized through the condensation of carbonyl compounds with amines [4, 5] (Figure 1a) and the reductive imination process involving nitroarenes and carbonyl compounds (Figure 1b) [22, 23]. Nonetheless, the high cost and instability of unsaturated ketones and aldehydes, combined with the difficulty in obtaining the necessary reactants, pose significant obstacles to the

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *Small Structures* published by Wiley-VCH GmbH.

FIGURE 1 | Conventional approaches for the synthesis of imines (C—N bond formation) from (a) coupling of aniline with aldehyde, (b) reductive coupling of nitroarenes with aldehydes, (c) coupling of amines with alcohols. (d) C—N bond formation via reductive coupling of substituted nitroarenes with alcohols and (e) comparison of TOF values of reported heterogeneous catalysts for the reductive coupling of nitrobenzene with alcohol (1-this work, 2 [6], 3 [7], 4 [8], 5 [9], 6 [10], 7 [11], 8 [12], 9 [13], 10 [14], 11 [15], 12 [16], 13 [17], 14 [18], 15 [19], 16 [20], and 17 [21]).

widespread application of this approach in the industrial sector [24]. In recent decades, considerable research has focused on developing environmentally benign methods for the synthesis of imine products with high selectivity and yield [25]. Among these efforts, the coupling of amines with alcohols has emerged as a key strategy, enabling the efficient formation of imine intermediates while generating water as the sole byproduct. (Figure 1c) [26]. In addition, the use of nitro compounds, which are more readily available and cost-effective, as substitutes for amines in imine synthesis would be of high interest [27]. In this context, coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols, a direct reductive coupling reaction allows for the efficient reduction of nitroarenes into amines via intramolecular hydride transfer from alcohol [28]. Subsequently deprotonated alcohol will be converted into aldehyde. Finally the obtained amine and alcohol couple together to form imine (C=N) product (Figure 1d). To meet the requirements of atom economy and green synthesis, the direct reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols can be achieved using a hydrogen borrowing strategy (referred to as a hydrogen auto transfer process) resulting in efficient imine synthesis [24, 29, 30]. Nevertheless, achieving high conversion and

imine selectivity along with the high process sustainability and atom economy possess a significant challenge.

There is increasing research interest in hydrogen-borrowing strategies, driven by their atom-economical and ecofriendly potential to enable the direct reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols to produce imines. Furthermore, alcohols and nitroarenes possess economical advantages due to their availability, affordability, and chemical stability [31, 32]. Due to these benefits, the direct reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols has garnered significant attention [27]. In the past decade, researchers have developed efficient noble metal-based heterogeneous catalysts for the direct reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols. For example, Au/Ag-Mo nanorods fabricated by Cui et al. [21], and the synthesis of mesoporous polyacrylic acid supported silver (Ag-MCP-1) nanoparticles (NPs) designed by Mandi et al. [18]. These materials have been utilized as catalysts for the reductive coupling of nitrobenzene and alcohols, with K₂CO₃ as a base and glycerol serving as the hydrogen source. Furthermore, Tang et al. have designed Palladium /deoxyribonucleic acid (Pd/DNA) catalysts that are remarkably active and selective in

the coupling of alcohols and nitroarenes into imines, using LiOH-H₂O as a base [20]. Moreover, a recyclable catalyst composed of hydrotalcite (HT) support and palladium (Pd/HT) NPs has been developed by Chen et al. [19], for the convenient synthesis of imines using benzyl alcohol and nitroarenes in toluene solvent. A recent development involves the synthesis of metal oxide supported noble metal bimetallic nanoalloys for one pot synthesis of amines [21]. In this context, Salarinejad et al. and Sankar et al. have demonstrated innovative Pd- and Au-based catalyst for the transformation of nitrobenzene and benzyl alcohol into imines such as N-benzylideneaniline. These systems include palladium NPs immobilized on core@double-shell magnetic nitrogen-doped carbon nanotubes (Fe₃O₄@N-C/Pd 5%) [13] and gold-palladium nanoalloys dispersed over TiO₂ (1% Au-Pd/TiO₂), respectively [17]. These catalytic systems successfully produced the imines through the reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols. However, as aforementioned catalytic process poses several drawbacks including the use of expensive noble metals, excessive exogenous base, organic solvents, longer reaction time, and additional hydrogen source. Subsequently, this increases the overall process costs and additionally produce a large amount of waste, which is not suitable for larger scale production of imines.

Considering the overall reported work, which is focused on the application of noble metal catalysts, including Ag, Au, and Pd. There is need for the development of an affordable, recyclable, and universally applicable catalytic system for the reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols, which would be greatly advantageous in terms of both the atom economy and environmental sustainability. However, to date there are few reports of nonprecious metal catalysts for the reductive coupling of alcohols and nitroarenes, and these all have low catalytic efficiencies [17–21, 33, 34]. Recently, Liu and his group developed cobalt-based catalyst (i.e., Co-N-C/CNT@AC) [15] and Zhou and his team fabricated cobalt-nitrogen/carbon catalyst (Co-N_x/C-800-AT) for the production of imines through the reductive coupling of nitroarenes with benzyl alcohol [16]. Moreover, Panja et al. have successfully synthesized a cobalt catalyst (Co-phen/C-800) for the dehydrogenative coupling of alcohols with nitroarenes, resulting in imine as a final product [14]. However, all these catalytic systems required longer reaction time to achieve desired conversion and selectivity, at higher metal utilization. Additionally, they explored very limited substrate scope for the synthesis of imines.

Recently, single-atom catalysts (SACs) have emerged as an effective alternative for nanocatalysts due to their higher catalytic efficiency, maximum atom utilization, and unique catalytic properties [35–37]. Due to the limited availability of metals, it is necessary to reduce the size of NPs to a single-atom. This approach not only enhances the utilization of active metal sites, but also improves catalytic efficiency, reduces metal consumption, and improve product selectivity [38, 39]. The growing importance of SACs in heterogeneous catalysis for organic transformations can be attributed to their impressive features [36]. These features can be significantly enhance the catalytic reductive coupling reaction of nitroarenes with benzyl alcohol. Recently, Zhang and his colleague developed a hierarchical nanopyramid structure for the reductive coupling [12]. This structure involves the immobilization of cobalt single-atoms on highly dispersed ZnO NPs, which are supported by nitrogen-doped carbon (Co-ZnO/NC). This catalyst exhibited

remarkable catalytic performance, leading to a 94% nitrobenzene conversion with 97% imine selectivity in toluene that resulted into TOF is 8.8 h⁻¹. Similarly, they developed advanced acid–base pairs of adjacent Co single-atoms ZnO nanoclusters (Co-ZnO ABPC) for coupling of alcohol and nitroarenes in toluene at 160°C resulted into very low TOF (8.01 h⁻¹) [11]. Furthermore, Zhang et al. achieved efficient transfer hydrogenation for selective imines synthesis by fabricating single-atom Co sites on N-doped carbon (Co SA/NC) with an upshifted d-band center [10]. On the other hand, aforementioned SACs systems had several drawbacks such as requires organic solvent, significant amount of metal loading (i.e. Co and Zn metals), and complexity to the synthesis process of SACs. Recently, Lui et al. designed Co/NC-1100 and Chen et al. have fabricated Co_{SA}-Co_{NC}/CN SACs explored for reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohol [8, 9]. However, these transformations require inert atmosphere and toxic organic solvents, resulting in a tedious process that was environmentally unsuitable and exhibited a very low TOF (Figure 1e). In order to advance the principles of atom economy and environmental sustainability, there is a strong need to develop a cost-effective, recyclable, and universally applicable catalytic system that does not require solvents, external bases, or hydrogen sources for the reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohols. In accordance with the aforementioned principles of economic and environmental sustainability, iron (Fe) catalysts meet the requirements as a readily available, abundant, and less toxic metal that demonstrates excellent hydrogen borrowing capability [36, 40, 41]. According to the previous report, it has been found that N-doped graphene (NG) acts as an advanced support that not only stabilizes and uniformly disperses Fe single-atoms, but also enhances the catalytic activity and selectivity in advanced organic reactions [42, 43]. Therefore, iron-based SACs are considered optimal selections for the reductive coupling of nitroarenes with alcohol under base and solvent-free environment.

Based on advanced properties of Fe SACs and NG support, we developed a cost-effective and earth-abundant heterogeneous Fe single-atom decorated on N-doped graphene (Fe₁@NG) catalysts via ion adsorption followed by microwave heating. Due to its unique composition and structure, the Fe₁@NG catalyst demonstrated exceptional catalytic activity and selectivity in the microwave-assisted reductive coupling of nitroarenes with benzyl alcohol and its derivatives, without the use of external base, hydrogen source, or solvents. Additionally, it exhibited a high TOF of ≈150 h⁻¹, which is significantly higher than the reported studies (Figure 1e). Furthermore, Fe₁@NG facilitates the transformation of benzyl alcohol and nitrobenzene derivatives into imines, even on a Gram-scale, making it suitable for industrial processes. The mechanistic pathway was investigated through experimental and DFT analysis. Notably, the DFT study revealed that, on the Fe₁-N₄ catalyst, benzyl alcohol is oxidized to benzaldehyde while 4-nitrophenol is simultaneously reduced to 4-aminophenol, which subsequently couples with the intermediate benzaldehyde to form the imine product. The combination of well-defined single-atom metal sites and π–π interactions creates an optimal platform for selective hydrogen transfer and efficient imine formation. To the best of our knowledge, the Fe₁@NG catalyst has demonstrated high catalytic performance compared to both noble and non-noble metal-based catalysts in the imination reaction (Table S5).

2 | Results and Discussion

2.1 | Synthesis and Characterization of Catalysts

The Fe₁@NG catalyst was fabricated using a two-step process involving ion adsorption followed by subsequent microwave heating (Figure 2a). Initially, NG was prepared through the pyrolysis of composite of g-C₃N₄ and glucose as a precursors. Fe salt was then impregnated into aqueous solution of NG via ion adsorption. Afterward, the obtained composite mixture was subjected to microwave treatment and subsequently freeze-dried resulting the Fe₁@NG catalyst [41]. Similarly, Fe_{NP}@NG catalyst was fabricated using same procedure, without the microwave irradiation for comparative study (for detailed procedure see experimental section 2 in Supporting Information) [41].

Extensive characterization study were performed to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the specific performance and structural features of Fe₁@NG catalyst. The NG, Fe_{NP}@NG and Fe₁@NG were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) showing two broad peaks at around 25° and 43° corresponding to the (002) and (101) diffraction planes of either amorphous carbon materials and/or N-doped graphene (Figure 2b) [44–46]. In contrast, XRD pattern of Fe_{NP}@NG, illustrated a small peak appeared at ≈35° which corresponding to plane (311) of iron oxide (FeO_x) materials (Figure 2b) [47, 48]. Furthermore, Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra of NG, Fe_{NP}@NG and Fe₁@NG revealed the absorption bands at ≈3437 cm⁻¹ (O-H), ≈2925 cm⁻¹ (C-H), ≈1628 cm⁻¹ (C=N/C=C), ≈1418 cm⁻¹ (N-H), ≈1258 cm⁻¹ (C-N), and ≈1105 cm⁻¹ (C-O), which represent the wide functional groups involved in the

FIGURE 2 | (a) Schematic synthesis of Fe₁@NG catalyst. (b) XRD pattern, (c) FT-IR spectra, and (d) Raman spectra of NG and Fe₁@NG. (e) HR-TEM image, (f) HAADF-STEM image (Fe single-atoms dispersed on NG showing in yellow circles), (g) HAADF-STEM image, and corresponding (h–j) STEM-EDX elemental color mapping of Fe₁@NG.

structure of the NG support (Figure 2c). Additionally, Fe_{NP}@NG exhibits a low-intensity vibration at $\approx 475\text{ cm}^{-1}$, confirming the presence of iron oxide species (Figure 2c) [45]. The Raman spectra of the catalysts demonstrated the presence of two distinct peaks, with the D band located at approximately 1346 cm^{-1} and the G band is at around 1590 cm^{-1} in NG and Fe₁@NG, respectively [49]. The formation of these peaks can be ascribed to either disordered carbon or lattice defects, along with graphitic sp²-hybridized carbon (Figure 2d). As result obtained from XRD, FT-IR, and Raman analyses confirmed that the NG was successfully prepared through the calcination process. The morphology of the Fe₁@NG catalyst was assessed by HR-TEM analysis. As shown in Figure S3a–d, HR-TEM images display transparent sheets with a wrinkled morphology, and there is no Fe NPs observed in the Fe₁@NG catalyst due to the microwave treatment, which helps evenly distribution of Fe single-atoms on NG support. The SAED image of the Fe₁@NG catalysts displayed a ring structure, suggesting the amorphous nature of catalyst (Figure S3f). Additionally, the HR-TEM image at high resolution did not detect any small Fe clusters in the Fe₁@NG catalyst, indicating the possibility of Fe single-atoms on the NG support (Figure 2e). Moreover, Fe single-atoms were confirmed using the high-angle annular dark-field scanning tunneling electron microscope (HAADF-STEM). The HAADF-STEM images reveal the atomic dispersion of Fe single-atoms on the NG support in the Fe₁@NG catalyst, as indicated by the yellow circles (Figure 2f). Furthermore, the HAADF-STEM image (Figure 2g) and STEM energy dispersive X-ray elemental analysis showed no significant clusters or NPs, with Fe, N, and C elements observed to be highly dispersed in Fe₁@NG catalyst matrix (Figure 2h–j).

Additionally, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to investigate the composition and chemical states of Fe, N, and C in the surface layers of Fe_{NP}@NG and Fe₁@NG catalysts. The XPS survey scan revealed that Fe, N, C and O peaks were predominantly present in Fe₁@NG and Fe_{NP}@NG catalysts (Figure S4a,b). The six distinct peaks were observed in the high-resolution Fe 2p spectrum of Fe₁@NG, with energy values of 711.7 and 725.5 eV assigned to Fe⁺². Furthermore, Fe⁺³ is indicated by peaks at 713.5 and 727.8 eV, accompanied by two satellite peaks at 718.6 and 733.5 eV (Figure 3a) [50].

Furthermore, the absence of a peak at 706.7 eV in both the Fe 2p spectra indicated that there is no zero-valent Fe in the Fe₁@NG and Fe_{NP}@NG catalysts [51]. In the N 1s deconvolution analysis of Fe₁@NG, five distinct peaks were observed at specific binding energies: 398.15 eV (representing pyridinic-N), 399.42 eV (corresponding to Fe-N_x), 400.99 eV (indicating pyrrolic-N), 402.2 eV (associated with graphitic-N), and 404.9 eV (representing oxidized-N) (Figures 3b and S4d) [52, 53]. Furthermore, the C 1s deconvolution of both Fe₁@NG and Fe_{NP}@NG catalysts exhibited four significant peaks at 284.8 (C=C/C-C), 285.9 (C=O/C=N), and 287.7 eV (C-O/C-N), all of which were observed at the same positions (Figures 3c and S4e). The C 1s spectra results shows that there were no noticeable changes in the NG support after Fe was loaded onto it, indicating that the NG support remains stable. It is also noticed that the composition of Fe₁@NG and Fe_{NP}@NG catalysts varied after the loading of Fe NPs as well as Fe single-atoms (Figure 3d). The composition of pyridinic-N, Fe-N_x, and graphitic-N is slightly higher in Fe₁@NG compared to the

Fe_{NP}@NG catalyst, i.e., 23.48%, 18.32%, and 15.48% in Fe₁@NG and 23.05%, 16.25%, and 9.70% in Fe_{NP}@NG catalysts, respectively. This reveals that the isolated Fe atoms are strongly coordinated with pyridinic-N and graphitic-N sites of NG support. Furthermore, the oxidized-N composition is decreased in the Fe₁@NG catalyst compared to the Fe_{NP}@NG catalyst (Table S1).

Additionally, chemical state, local geometry as well as electronic structure of the Fe single-atom in Fe₁@NG catalyst were further investigated by using the X-ray absorption spectrometry (XAS). The X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) spectra of Fe₁@NG has a small pre-edge peak, which is due to a dipole forbidden transition from 1s to 3d transition, at 7.114 keV, consistent with that of Fe⁺³ reference compounds, (Figure 3e and Table S2) [41]. To determine the local coordination of Fe in Fe₁@NG, the EXAFS analysis was performed. The k²-weighted EXAFS fit gave four Fe–N bonds at 2.00 Å, with no higher shell peaks. In the FT-XAFS spectra of Fe₁@NG, a distinct primary peak is observed at $\approx 2.00\text{ Å}$, indicating the presence of Fe–N scattering and the lack of Fe–Fe bonding (2.48 Å). There is also a small higher shell Fe–O–Fe peak at 3.06 Å suggesting Fe₁@NG has a small amount of Fe₂O₃. Since the latter has six Fe–O bonds, and the coordination number is near 4, this suggests that there is only a small amount of the Fe⁺³ oxide. Based on combined XAS analysis, the Fe₁@NG catalyst is a single Fe⁺³ ion bonded to the four N atoms of the support resulted into Fe₁–N₄ coordination (Figure 3f and Table S2) [41].

Further, textural properties of the Fe_{NP}@NG and Fe₁@NG catalysts were investigated using the N₂ adsorption–desorption analysis. The Fe₁@NG exhibited a higher specific surface area ($778\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$) and pore volume ($0.23\text{ cm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$) as compared to Fe_{NP}@NG and NG support (Figure 3g,h, Table S3), respectively. Figure 3i depicts the 3D model image of an isolated Fe atom coordinated with four nitrogen atoms (Fe₁–N₄ coordination). Typically, catalysts that have a low specific surface area, such as Fe_{NP}@NG catalysts, exhibit weaker catalytic activity because the low surface active sites are not sufficiently exposed in reaction. Furthermore, the loading of Fe in Fe_{NP}@NG and Fe₁@NG determined by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) is 1.7 and 1.0 wt%, respectively. Even with a low iron loading, the Fe₁@NG catalyst demonstrates superior catalytic performance compared to Fe_{NP}@NG, primarily due to its low loading uniformly distributed Fe active sites, which maximize substrate accessibility on the NG support.

The aforementioned characterization of the Fe₁@NG catalyst revealed that the uniformly dispersed Fe single-atoms anchored on NG, exhibited an Fe⁺³ oxidation state with a well-defined Fe₁–N₄ configuration. The atomically distributed Fe active sites, high surface area, and optimized pore structure can be beneficial to its remarkable performance in the reductive coupling of nitroarenes with benzyl alcohol.

2.2 | Optimization of Reductive Coupling of 4-Methyl Nitrotoluene with Benzyl Alcohol

Initially, we optimize the catalytic systems and reaction conditions for the C=N bond formation via reductive coupling. The reductive coupling of 4-methyl nitrobenzene with benzyl alcohol in a 1:8 molar ratio was selected as model reaction for

FIGURE 3 | XPS deconvolution: (a) F 2p, (b) N 1s, and (c) C 1s of Fe₁@NG. (d) Nitrogen composition of Fe_{NP}@NG and Fe₁@NG catalyst. (e) Fe K-edge XANES of Fe₁@NG catalyst (blue), Fe foil (black), and Fe(AcAc)₃ reference (red). (f) k²-weighted Fourier transform of the Fe K edge EXAFS of Fe₁@NG catalyst, solid line-magnitude of FT and dotted line-imaginary part FT. BET surface area and pore size analysis: (g) Nitrogen (N₂) adsorption-desorption isotherms. (h) Pore size distribution in Fe₁@NG structure. (i) Model of Fe₁@NG catalyst.

optimization study. Initially, we conducted the reductive coupling reaction between 4-methyl nitrobenzene (1a) and benzyl alcohol (2a) in the absence of a catalyst, resulting in a significantly low conversion (5%) toward the desired imine (3a) product (Table 1, entry 1). Moreover, this particular model reaction was conducted solely with NG support, leading to a notably low conversion (13%) (Table 1, entry 2). In addition, the reductive coupling reaction conducted on Fe_{NP}@NG catalyst resulted in a 37% conversion of 4-methyl nitrobenzene to the desired product (Table 1, entry 3). In addition, it is worth mentioning that the Fe₁@NG catalyst exhibited an impressive conversion of 95% for 4-methylnitrobenzene, resulting in a highly selective imine product with 85% selectivity (Table 1, entry 4). The conversion and selectivity of the reductive coupling reaction is enhanced by the presence of uniformly dispersed Fe single-atoms on the NG of the Fe₁@NG catalyst, which provides a more potentially active-site for the conversion of benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde and reduction of nitroarenes to amines in comparison to the Fe_{NP}@NG catalyst (Table 1, entry 3). Further reaction time was optimized at 2.5 and 3.5 h, resulting in 91% and 96%

conversion of 4-methylnitrobenzene to imine product, respectively (Table 1, entries 5 and 6). Following this, the optimization of Fe₁@NG catalyst quantity was performed at 5 and 15 mg, resulting in 46% and 96% conversion toward the targeted product, respectively (Table 1, entries 7 and 8). Furthermore, reaction temperature was optimized for the imination reaction at 150°C and 170°C, resulting in 77% and 95% conversion of 4-methylnitrobenzene to imine product with 83% and 73% selectivity, respectively (Table 1, entries 9 and 10). Despite the optimization of 3.5 h (Table 1, entry 6), the use of a 15 mg catalyst quantity (Table 1, entry 8) and 170°C temperature (Table 1, entry 10), resulting in the same conversion, i.e., 95%–96%, however, there has been a noticeable decrease in the selectivity of imine products. This can be attributed to the tendency of Fe single-atoms to transfer hydrogen to the imine product. The imination reaction, conducted with 0.5 mmol of 4-methylnitrobenzene, exhibited a noteworthy enhancement in conversion (i.e., 99%). However, the low selectivity (i.e., 50%) toward the imine product experienced a decrease as a result of the effective activation of Fe single-atom, leading to further hydrogenation of the imine to the

TABLE 1 | Optimization table for microwave-assisted reductive coupling of 4-methyl nitrobenzene with benzyl alcohol.^a

Entry	Catalyst	Temp., °C	Time, h	Conv., %	3a Sel., %	4a Sel., %
1	—	160	3.0	05	93	07
2	NG	160	3.0	13	90	10
3	Fe _{NP} @NG	160	3.0	37	91	09
4	Fe ₁ @NG	160	3.0	95	85	12
5	Fe ₁ @NG	160	2.5	91	79	16
6	Fe ₁ @NG	160	3.5	96	80	17
7 ^b	Fe ₁ @NG	160	3.0	46	88	06
8 ^c	Fe ₁ @NG	160	3.0	96	77	17
9	Fe ₁ @NG	150	3.0	77	83	12
10	Fe ₁ @NG	170	3.0	95	73	23
11 ^d	Fe ₁ @NG	160	3.0	99	50	50
12 ^e	Fe ₁ @NG	160	3.0	89	79	21
13 ^f	Fe ₁ @NG	160	3.0	00	00	00

^aReaction conditions: 4-methyl nitrobenzene (1 mmol), benzyl alcohol (8 mmol), catalyst (10 mg) in microwave (MW) reactor (Model: CEM SP Discover and power 120 W). Conversion and selectivity were calculated using nitroarenes as the limiting reagent, based on gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) analysis.

^bCatalyst amount – 05 mg.

^cCatalyst amount – 15 mg.

^dSubstrate amount - 0.5 mmol of 4-methyl nitrobenzene.

^eN₂ gas purging for 5 min.

^fThermal condition.

secondary amine product (Table 1, entry 11). This control experiment also proved that the reduction of nitroarene is rate limiting step in the reductive coupling reaction employed for the imine production.

Furthermore, the reductive coupling reaction was conducted under an inert N₂ atmosphere. However, no significant changes were observed in the conversion (i.e., 89%) and selectivity (i.e., 79%) of the imine product (Table 1, entry 12). In the end, the reaction was carried out at a temperature of 160°C under thermal conditions (without microwave use), surprisingly, there was no conversion of nitroarenes and alcohol into imine product (Table 1, entry 13). This proves that the microwave heating has significant impact on the activation of the reactants as well as Fe₁@NG catalyst, thus facilitating the progression of the imination reaction. In conclusion, Table 1, entry 4 demonstrates that the microwave radiation, i.e., noncontact, volumetric equal, and fast heating effectively increases the efficiency of the Fe₁@NG catalyst, and subsequently rate of reaction in the reductive coupling of 4-methyl nitrobenzene with benzyl alcohol under optimal conditions in comparison with thermal or conventional heating.

2.3 | Substrate Scope

Taking inspiration from the optimized reaction conditions, we investigated the universality of our catalytic protocol for synthesizing several imine derivatives via reductive coupling. In the substrate scope study, a wide variety of structurally diverse

nitrobenzene and benzyl alcohol derivatives were used as starting materials in presence of Fe₁@NG catalyst at 160°C for 3 h in MW reactor (Table 2). Initially, the nitrobenzene underwent smooth reactions with electron-donating groups, such as *para* or *meta* —CH₃, —OCH₃, and —OH substituted nitrobenzenes and benzyl alcohols, resulting in imine products with high conversion (around 88%–99%) with 81%–99% selectivity (Table 2, 3a–e). After the imination reactions, regioisomers of methyl nitrobenzene with benzyl alcohols revealed that the conversion was influenced by the substituted position on the nitrobenzene ring. It was observed that the *para*-substituted nitrobenzene exhibited higher conversion compared to the *meta*-substituted nitrobenzene. This observation suggests that the reaction is strongly influenced by steric hindrance of metal substituted groups (Table 2, 3a,c). The substitution of nitrobenzene at the *para* position with electron-donating groups such as —OCH₃ and —OH, along with the use of benzyl alcohol, resulted in a notable increase in conversion (97%–99%). This can be attributed to the electron-donating inductive effect of *para*-substituted methoxy and hydroxy nitrobenzene (Table 2, 3d,e). In the subsequent set of experiments, the reaction of halonitrobenzene with *para*-substituted groups such as —F, —Cl, and —Br in the presence of benzyl alcohol, resulted in the formation of the desired imines with 62%–90% conversion and 67%–99% selectivity (Table 2, 3f–h). In the case of nitrobenzene substituted with electron-withdrawing groups and benzyl alcohol, the reactivity decreased in the sequence of —F > —Cl > —Br. This trend implies the presence of an

TABLE 2 | Exploration of microwave assisted reductive coupling of nitrobenzene derivatives with benzyl alcohol derivatives on Fe₁@NG catalyst.^{a,b}

^aReaction conditions: Nitroarene derivatives (1 mmol), alcohol (8 mmol), Fe₁@NG (10 mg), 3 h at 160°C in microwave (MW) reactor (Model: CEM SP Discover and power 120 W).

^b140°C and 2.5 h. Conversion and selectivity were evaluated by GC-MS, considering the nitroarene substrate as the limiting reagent.

electron-withdrawing inductive effect as well as a decrease in electronegativity (Table 2, 3f–h). In addition, it is worth mentioning that the reaction activities of nitrobenzene with *meta* and *para* positions of —COCH₃ and —CH=CH₂ groups in combination with benzyl alcohol exhibited a 96%–99% conversion that resulted in the selective formation of imine products with a 82%–91% selectivity, respectively. This high catalytic performance was achieved without any interference from the metal and with *para*-substituted —COCH₃ and —CH=CH₂ groups, respectively (Table 2, 3i,j).

Moreover, benzyl alcohol substituted with both electron-donating groups (-OCH₃) and nitrobenzene containing electron-donating groups (*p* or *m*-CH₃, and -OCH₃) can be efficiently converted into the corresponding imines through transfer hydrogenation, resulting in moderate conversion

(i.e., 62%–84%) and excellent selectivity (i.e., 74%–99%), as indicated in Table 2, entries 3k–n. This could be due to the electron donating effect of nitroarene and benzyl alcohol substituents. Additionally, the desired imine products were obtained with a 56%–88% conversion and 78%–82% selectivity by reacting 4-fluoro and 4-chloro nitrobenzene with 4-methoxy benzyl alcohol, as shown in Table 2, 3o,p. It is also important to highlight that the reductive coupling reactions between 4-methoxy benzyl alcohol and nitrobenzene's substituents at the *meta* and *para* position i.e., —COCH₃ and —CH=H₂, exhibited 84%–99% conversion and resulted in the preferential formation of imine products with 72%–88% selectivity without affecting acetyl and vinyl group (Table 2, 3q,r). This proves that acetyl and vinyl groups do not directly affect the conversion and selectivity of imines formation.

It is noteworthy that the synthesis of allyl imine, achieved through the reductive coupling reaction between cinnamyl alcohol and nitrobenzene, demonstrated exceptional selectivity (99%) and conversion efficiency (99%), while preserving the —C=C— bond of the allyl imine product (Table 2, 3s). Furthermore, the reductive coupling reaction of heteroaromatic alcohols, such as 2-pyridine methanol, with nitrobenzene has demonstrated remarkable conversion (99%) and 82% selectivity towards the desired imine product (Table 2, 3t).

Several reports have been published documenting the reductive coupling of nitroarenes and alcohols, resulting in the formation of imine products. According to literature, previous studies have utilized noble and non-noble metal-based catalysts such as Au/Ag–Mo–NR [21], Pd/DNA [20], Pd/HT [19], Ag-MCP-1 [18], 1%Au–Pd/TiO₂ [17], Fe₃O₄@N-C/Pd_{5%} [13], Co-N_x/C-800-AT [16], Co-NC/CNT@AC [15], Co-phen/C-800 [14], MgO/NC-500 [6], Co-ZnO/NC [12], and Co-ZnO ABPC [11]. Additionally, exogenous bases including Cs₂CO₃, K₂CO₃, and LiOH·H₂O, as well as organic solvents such as toluene and mesitylene, were employed. Moreover, the reactions were carried out under an inert N₂ gas atmosphere. However, these reaction conditions make catalytic system costly, challenging

to isolate the desired imine product and limit the substrate scope study. Moreover, the TOF of the previously mentioned catalysts exhibited a notable lower when compared to the Fe₁@NG (TOF, $\approx 150 \text{ h}^{-1}$) catalyst in the reductive coupling of nitroarene with benzyl alcohol to corresponding imine product (Table S5).

The effectiveness of this catalytic protocol in synthetic applications has been demonstrated through imination of nitrobenzene and benzyl alcohol derivatives, resulting in exceptional conversion and selectivity toward the formation of imine products. To demonstrate the suitability of the catalyst for industrial scale implementation, the catalytic protocol for the microwave-assisted reductive coupling of benzyl alcohol with a nitrobenzene derivative on Fe₁@NG catalyst through the utilization of a hydrogen borrowing strategy was validated on a Gram-scale. Remarkable outcomes are achieved in Gram-scale reactions, particularly in the imination reaction involving benzyl alcohol and nitrobenzene derivatives. The conversion are consistently excellent, ranging from 60%–99%, and the desired imine product is selectively obtained with selectivities in the range of 80%–99%, as depicted in (Figure 4a).

FIGURE 4 | (a) Gram-scale reaction of microwave assisted reductive coupling on Fe₁@NG catalyst. ^aReaction conditions: Nitroarenes (10 mmol), benzyl alcohol (40 mmol), Fe₁@NG (100 mg), 6 h at 160°C and microwave (MW) reactor (Model: CEM SP Discover and power 120 W). Conversion and selectivity were calculated based on nitroarenes by GC-MS analysis. (b) Proposed reaction mechanism for the reductive coupling of 4-nitrophenol and benzyl alcohol over Fe₁@NG catalyst based on DFT study (Carbon shown as gray sphere, oxygen in red, nitrogen in blue, hydrogen in white, iron in other).

2.4 | Unraveling Reaction Mechanisms via DFT Analysis and Experimental Study

Guided by experimental observations, a detailed reaction mechanism was modeled for the Fe₁@NG-catalyzed reductive coupling of 4-nitrophenol (as nitroarenes representative) with benzyl alcohol to yield 4-(benzylideneamino)phenol. As illustrated in Figure 4b, the reaction proceeds through several intermediate compounds, whose presence was corroborated by GC-MS analysis (Figures S6 and S7), and whose geometries and relative energetics were further evaluated computationally.

The pristine Fe₁@NG catalyst (I-a) readily adsorbs benzyl alcohol (I-b), forming a stable chemisorbed intermediate (II) with a strong adsorption energy of -50.3 kcal/mol. The interaction with a Fe₁-N₄ site interaction facilitates the abstraction of a hydroxyl proton, initiating the activation process. In addition to metal-ligand coordination, π - π interactions between the aromatic reactants and the conjugated NG support not only significantly stabilize key intermediates but may also promote orbital alignment necessary for efficient electron transfer, thereby modulating both the thermodynamics and selectivity of the reaction.

Subsequent structural reorganization on the catalyst surface involves the exothermic proton migration from hydroxyl to a nearby nitrogen site (-7.7 kcal/mol, III), priming the system for the approach and coadsorption of the second substrate, 4-nitrophenol (I-c) (-30.2 kcal/mol, IV). This enables a step-wise reduction to 4-nitrosophenol, initiated by an endothermic hydride transfer to the nitro group (13.5 kcal/mol, V), followed by a proton transfer from deprotonated benzyl alcohol (-27.2 kcal/mol, VI) and accompanied by the elimination of water. This second exothermic step yields 4-nitrosophenol (VII-a) and benzaldehyde (VII-b), accompanied by the elimination of water. Desorption of the formed 4-nitrosophenol requires energy of 19.9 kcal/mol and represents a key intermediate that reenters the reaction cycle.

Steps VIII-XIII represent a branching pathway, involving coupling between the intermediate III and 4-nitrosophenol (VII-a) to generate 4-aminophenol (XIII). This occurs via coadsorption of 4-nitrosophenol on state III (-29.8 kcal/mol, VIII), exothermic hydride transfer to the nitroso group (IX, -9.8 kcal/mol), followed by proton transfer from deprotonated benzyl alcohol (-30.3 kcal/mol, X). Further, the intermediate XI readsorb on state III which results in a highly exothermic step, including subsequent interaction with additional hydride and deprotonated benzyl alcohol (-81.9 kcal/mol, XII) to form and then release 4-aminophenol (23.0 kcal/mol, XIII) with concomitant water elimination. Finally, the condensation of formed benzaldehyde with 4-aminophenol yields the targeted imine product (-13.3 kcal/mol, XIV), completing the cycle. It should be noted that 4-methylaniline may couple to azobenzene derivative, which is also experimentally observed byproduct with GC-MS (Figure S6). Further to strengthen the DFT-assisted mechanism, we also performed control experiments using benzyl alcohol as the sole substrate, resulting in a 7% conversion to benzaldehyde with 99% selectivity. Additionally, the reductive coupling of 4-nitrophenol with benzyl alcohol yielded a 99% conversion and 99% selectivity toward the corresponding imine product (Table S4). The experimental results revealed that, the reaction proceeds via a benzaldehyde intermediate, ultimately leading to imine formation.

Overall, the Fe₁@NG catalyst enables a multistep transformation with convenient thermodynamic feasibility while maintaining the structural integrity of the Fe-N₄ coordination environment throughout the reaction. This suggests a high level of active-site stability and catalyst recyclability. Moreover, the synergistic contribution of π - π interactions and well-defined single-atom coordination provides an ideal platform for selective hydrogen transfer and imine formation under mild, microwave assisted, base/solvent-free conditions.

Key substrates, intermediates, and products (I-XV) were optimized using DFT, and their electronic reaction energies (in kcal/mol) are indicated. The mechanism involves initial adsorption and activation of benzyl alcohol, followed by coadsorption and interaction with 4-nitrophenol via proton/hydride transfers and water eliminations. The final imine product is formed through condensation of benzaldehyde with 4-aminophenol. π - π interactions and Fe-N₄ coordination in Fe₁@NG catalyst contribute to intermediate stabilization and pathway selectivity.

2.5 | Catalyst Recycling Study

Reusability is a crucial factor in evaluating the practical applicability and economic feasibility of heterogeneous catalysts. The stability and catalytic activity of the synthesized Fe₁@NG catalyst were investigated. The catalyst exhibited sustained performance over four cycles, followed by a slightly decline in conversion and selectivity in the subsequent cycle (Figure S5a). After the reactions, reused catalyst was characterized by XRD, XPS and HR-TEM analyses. In the XRD pattern, no additional peaks were observed. However, in the deconvoluted XPS spectra of Fe, a small peak appeared at 707 and 720 eV respectively attributed to the Fe⁰ NPs due to change in oxidation state from Fe⁺³ to Fe⁰. This could be due to the impact of rapid microwave heating along with the benzyl alcohol as a reducing agent (Figure S5b,c) [54]. Previous studies revealed that the benzyl alcohol act as a reducing agent for the synthesis of metal oxides in presence of microwave heating [55]. Additionally, in this work, initially benzyl alcohol is typically oxidized to benzaldehyde under microwave heating, while a hydride transfer takes place to reduce the nitro group to an amine, confirmed through control experiments and DFT studies. Additionally, it is a possibility of transferring these hydrogen/electrons to Fe⁺³ species in the presence of rapid, and selective microwave heating resulting in the reduction of Fe⁺³ to Fe⁰ [41]. Furthermore, a comparison of HR-TEM images of fresh and reused Fe₁@NG catalyst samples confirmed the presence of newly formed tiny Fe⁰ NPs (Figure S5d-g). Additionally, the Fe₁@NG catalyst displayed impressive reusability in Gram-scale reactions, consistently maintaining high catalytic performance for up to three cycles. However, after the third cycle, there is a decline in the catalytic activity due to the formation of Fe single-atoms into Fe NPs.

3 | Conclusion

In summary, we have successfully fabricated earth-abundant and sustainable Fe₁@NG catalyst via ion adsorption and microwave treatment. The HAADF-STEM, XANES, and FT-XAFS analyses clearly demonstrated that the presence of uniformly dispersed Fe single-atoms (Fe⁺³) coordinated with four nitrogen atoms

(Fe₁-N₄), effectively facilitating hydrogen borrowing to enhance the reductive coupling reaction on the Fe₁@NG catalyst. The Fe₁@NG catalyst exhibited exceptionally high catalytic performance compared to its nanoparticle counterpart, Fe_{NP}@NG. This superior activity is attributed to the homogeneous dispersion of isolated Fe atoms on the nitrogen-doped graphene support, which maximizes reactant accessibility and facilitates efficient hydrogen borrowing for imine formation. This catalyst efficiently and selectively synthesized over 20 imine products through the borrowing hydrogen strategy. Additionally, it demonstrated strong activity in Gram-scale reductive coupling of nitroarenes with benzyl alcohol, a promising process for the synthesis of imine intermediates in the pharmaceutical and agricultural applications. DFT studies revealed that benzyl alcohol is oxidized on the Fe₁-N₄ catalyst, transferring hydride and proton to simultaneously reduce 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol. The resulting 4-aminophenol then couples with the intermediate benzaldehyde to form the imine product. Furthermore, the catalyst's reusability was effectively demonstrated at the Gram-scale, consistently maintaining high catalytic performance over four consecutive cycles. The Fe₁@NG catalyst offers significant potential in promoting sustainable and cost-effective catalysis, which can be beneficial for industrial applications, especially in the synthesis of important C—N bonds and hydrogenation reactions.

Author Contributions

A.D.K. and M.B.G. conceived and proposed the research idea. A.D.K. conducted material synthesis, performed catalytic experiments, and contributed to methodology, visualization, data acquisition, data curation, and writing of the original manuscript draft. H.B.K. performed the experiments, analyzed the data, and reviewed and edited the manuscript. R.P.U. reviewed and edited the manuscript. S.J. and J.T.M. performed XAS analysis, and reviewed and edited the manuscript. R.L. and M.O. performed computational calculations, cowrote the section, and reviewed and edited the manuscript. Y.W. performed AC-HAADF STEM analysis, and reviewed and edited the manuscript. M.B.G. reviewed and edited the manuscript, visualization, funding acquisition, and supervised overall project. All authors discussed the experimental, characterization data, and commented on the manuscript.

Acknowledgments

A.D.K. would like to acknowledge the University Grants Commission, Delhi, for providing a NET-JRF and SRF fellowship to pursue a doctoral degree. H.B.K. and R.P.U. are grateful to Institute of Chemical Technology, Mumbai, for the "Tutor cum Research Associate" fellowship and Anusandhan National Research Foundation, Prime Minister Research fellowship (ANRF-PMRF), respectively for doctoral study. This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic through the e-INFRA CZ (ID:90254). M.O. acknowledges support by the ERDF/ESF project TECHSCALE (No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004587) by MEYS. M.O. also acknowledge financial support from the European Union through the REFRESH project – Research Excellence For Region Sustainability and High-tech Industries (CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048), funded via the Operational Programme Just Transition. This research used resources at the 8-ID beamline of the National Synchrotron Light Source II, a U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) Office of Science User Facility operated for the DOE Office of Science by Brookhaven National Laboratory under Contract no. DE-SC0012704.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

1. M. E. Belowicha and J. F. Stoddart, "Dynamic Imine Chemistry," *Chemical Society Reviews* 41 (2012): 2003.
2. S. Kobayashi and H. Ishitani, "Catalytic Enantioselective Addition to Imines," *Chemical Reviews* 99 (1999): 1069–1094.
3. B. Chen, L. Wang, and S. Gao, "Recent Advances in Aerobic Oxidation of Alcohols and Amines to Imines," *ACS Catalysis* 5, no. 10 (2015): 5851.
4. M. Hosseini-Sarvari, "Nano-Tube TiO₂ as a New Catalyst for Eco-friendly Synthesis of Imines in Sunlight," *Chinese Chemical Letters* 22, no. 5 (2011): 547.
5. H. Naeimi, F. Salimi, and K. Rabiei, "Mild and Convenient One Pot Synthesis of Schiff bases in the Presence of P₂O₅/Al₂O₃ as new catalyst under solvent-free conditions," *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical* 260, no. 1-2 (2006): 100.
6. Z. Yuan, B. Han, B. Liu, et al., "Unexpected Activity of MgO Nanoclusters for the Reductive-Coupling Synthesis of Organonitrogen Chemicals with C=N Bonds," *Nature Communications* 16, no. 1 (2025): 2963.
7. J. Song, C. Che, Y. Dai, et al., "Inducing Cu Charge Redistribution by Modulating Proximity with Zr(OH)₄ for Selective Synthesis of Imines and Secondary Amines with Stoichiometric Benzyl Alcohol and Nitrobenzene," *ACS Catalysis* 15, no. 2 (2025): 1170.
8. Z. Chen, S. Yang, J. Yang, et al., "Boosting Catalytic Hydrogen Transfer Cascade Reactions via Tandem Catalyst Design by Coupling Co Single Atoms with Adjacent Co Clusters," *ACS Catalysis* 14, no. 24 (2024): 18256.
9. X. Liu, L. Huang, Y. He, P. Zhou, X. Song, and Z. Zhang, "Single-Atom Co-N(4) Sites Mediate C=N Formation via Reductive Coupling of Nitroarenes with Alcohols," *JACS Au* 4, no. 9 (2024): 3436.
10. T. Zhang, W. Zhao, S. Li, et al., "Single-Atom Co Sites with Upshifted d-Band Center Efficiently Boost Transfer Hydrogenation for Selective Imines Synthesis," *Chemical Engineering Journal* 484 (2024): 149614.
11. Z. Chen, C. Wu, W. Li, et al., "Construction Co-ZnO Acid-Base Pair Catalysts for Alcohol and Nitrobenzene Hydrogen Transfer Cascade Reaction," *Applied Catalysis B: Environment and Energy* 340 (2024): 123203.
12. C. Wu, C. Zhu, K. Liu, et al., "Nano-Pyramid-Type Co-ZnO/NC for Hydrogen Transfer Cascade Reaction between Alcohols and Nitrobenzene," *Applied Catalysis B: Environment and Energy* 300 (2022): 120288.
13. N. Salarinejad, M. Dabiri, and S. K. Movahed, "A Novel Core@double Shell Magnetic Nitrogen-Doped Carbon Nanotubes as a Support for Palladium Nanoparticles: A Highly Efficient Magnetic Catalyst in the Direct Reductive Coupling of Nitroarenes and Alcohols," *Catalysis Communications* 172 (2022): 106529.
14. D. Panja, B. Paul, B. Balasubramaniam, R. K. Gupta, and S. Kundu, "Application of a Reusable Co-based Nanocatalyst in Alcohol Dehydrogenative Coupling Strategy: Synthesis of Quinoxaline and Imine Scaffolds," *Catalysis Communications* 137 (2020): 105927.
15. D. Liu, P. Yang, H. Zhang, et al., "Direct Reductive Coupling of Nitroarenes and Alcohols Catalysed by Co-N-C/CNT@AC," *Green Chemistry* 21, no. 8 (2019): 2129.
16. P. Zhou, L. Jiang, F. Wang, K. Deng, K. Lv, and Z. Zhang, "High Performance of a Cobalt-Nitrogen Complex for the Reduction and Reductive Coupling of Nitro Compounds into Amines and their Derivatives," *Science Advances* 3, no. 2 (2017): e1601945.

17. M. Sankar, Q. He, S. Dawson, et al., "Supported Bimetallic Nano-Alloys as Highly Active Catalysts for the One-Pot Tandem Synthesis of Imines and Secondary Amines from Nitrobenzene and Alcohols," *Catalysis Science & Technology* 6, no. 14 (2016): 5473.
18. U. Mandi, A. S. Roy, S. K. Kundu, S. Roy, A. Bhaumik, and S. M. Islam, "Mesoporous Polyacrylic Acid Supported Silver Nanoparticles as an Efficient Catalyst for Reductive Coupling of Nitrobenzenes and Alcohols using Glycerol as Hydrogen Source," *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 472 (2016): 202.
19. J. Chen, S. Huang, J. Lin, and W. Su, "Recyclable Palladium Catalyst for Facile Synthesis of Imines from Benzyl Alcohols and Nitroarenes," *Applied Catalysis A: General* 470 (2014): 1.
20. L. Tang, H. Sun, Y. Li, Z. Zha, and Z. Wang, "Highly Active and Selective Synthesis of Imines From Alcohols and Amines or Nitroarenes Catalyzed by Pd/DNA in Water With Dehydrogenation," *Green Chemistry* 14, no. 12 (2012): 3423.
21. X. Cui, C. Zhang, F. Shi, and Y. Deng, "Au/Ag-Mo Nano-Rods Catalyzed Reductive Coupling of Nitrobenzenes and Alcohols using Glycerol as the Hydrogen Source," *Chemical Communications* 48, no. 75 (2012): 9391.
22. C. Chen, R. Fan, M. Han, et al., "Tunable Synthesis of Imines and Secondary-Amines from Tandem Hydrogenation-Coupling of Aromatic Nitro and Aldehyde Over NiCo₅ Bi-Metallic Catalyst," *Applied Catalysis B: Environment and Energy* 280 (2021): 119448.
23. S. Huang, Z. Zhao, Z. Wei, et al., "Targeted Regulation of the Selectivity of Cascade Synthesis towards Imines/Secondary Amines by Carbon-Coated Co-based Catalysts," *Green Chemistry* 24, no. 18 (2022): 6945.
24. T. Irrgang and R. Kempe, "3d-Metal Catalyzed N- and C-Alkylation Reactions via Borrowing Hydrogen or Hydrogen Autotransfer," *Chemical Reviews* 119, no. 4 (2019): 2524.
25. Z. Li, X. Lu, R. Zhao, et al., "A Heterogeneous Single Atom Cobalt Catalyst for Highly Efficient Acceptorless Dehydrogenative Coupling Reactions," *Small* 19, no. 18 (2023): e2207941.
26. B. Chen, J. Li, W. Dai, L. Wang, and S. Gao, "Direct Imine Formation by Oxidative Coupling of Alcohols and Amines using Supported Manganese Oxides under an Air Atmosphere," *Green Chemistry* 16, no. 6 (2014): 3328.
27. D. Formenti, F. Ferretti, F. K. Scharnagl, and M. Beller, "Reduction of Nitro Compounds Using 3d-Non-Noble Metal Catalysts," *Chemical Reviews* 119, no. 4 (2019): 2611.
28. A. D. Kute, R. P. Gaikwad, I. R. Warkad, and M. B. Gawande, "A Review on the Synthesis and Applications of Sustainable Copper-based Nanomaterials," *Green Chemistry* 24, no. 9 (2022): 3502.
29. B. G. Reed-Berendt, D. E. Latham, M. B. Dambatta, and L. C. Morrill, "Borrowing Hydrogen for Organic Synthesis," *ACS Central Science* 7, no. 4 (2021): 570.
30. A. Corma, J. Navas, and M. J. Sabater, "Advances in One-Pot Synthesis through Borrowing Hydrogen Catalysis," *Chemical Reviews* 118, no. 4 (2018): 1410.
31. J. Campos, "Dehydrogenation of Alcohols and Polyols from a Hydrogen Production Perspective," *Physical Sciences Reviews* 3, no. 6 (2018): 25.
32. M. Trincado, D. Banerjee, and H. Grützmacher, "Molecular Catalysts for Hydrogen Production from Alcohols," *Energy & Environmental Science* 7, no. 8 (2014): 2464.
33. R. Cano, D. J. Ramon, and M. Yus, "Impregnated Ruthenium on Magnetite as a Recyclable Catalyst for the N-Alkylation of Amines, Sulfonamides, Sulfinamides, and Nitroarenes using Alcohols as Electrophiles by a Hydrogen Autotransfer Process," *Journal of Organic Chemistry* 76, no. 14 (2011): 5547.
34. L. Hu, H. Liu, and Z. Li, "Rational Design of Core-Shell Structured Pd@MIL-100(Fe) for Efficient Visible Light-Initiated Syntheses of Secondary Amines from Nitro Aromatics and Benzyl Alcohols," *ACS Catalysis* 15, no. 3 (2025): 2262.
35. H. B. Kale, A. D. Kute, R. P. Gaikwad, P. Fornasiero, R. Zbořil, and M. B. Gawande, "Synthesis and Energy Applications of Copper-based Single Atom Electrocatalysts," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* 502 (2024): 215602.
36. B. Singh, M. B. Gawande, A. D. Kute, et al., "Single-Atom (Iron-Based) Catalysts: Synthesis and Applications," *Chemical Reviews* 121, no. 21 (2021): 13620.
37. H. Wang, T. Yang, J. Wang, Z. Zhou, Z. Pei, and S. Zhao, "Coordination Engineering in Single-Site Catalysts: General Principles, Characterizations, and Recent Advances," *Chem* 10, no. 1 (2024): 48.
38. A. Bakandritsos, R. G. Kadam, P. Kumar, et al., "Mixed-Valence Single-Atom Catalyst Derived from Functionalized Graphene," *Advanced Materials* 31, no. 17 (2019): e1900323.
39. R. G. Kadam, M. Medved, S. Kumar, et al., "Linear-Structure Single-Atom Gold(I) Catalyst for Dehydrogenative Coupling of Organosilanes with Alcohols," *ACS Catalysis* 13, no. 24 (2023): 16067.
40. B. Singh, V. Sharma, R. P. Gaikwad, P. Fornasiero, R. Zboril, and M. B. Gawande, "Single-Atom Catalysts: A Sustainable Pathway for the Advanced Catalytic Applications," *Small* 17, no. 16 (2021): e2006473.
41. A. D. Kute, H. B. Kale, P. Sharma, et al., "Iron Single-Atom Catalyzed N-Alkylation of Amines with Alcohols via Solvent-Free Borrowing Hydrogen Strategy," *Advanced Science* 12, no. 46 (2025): e07915.
42. Y. Tang, W. Chen, B. Wu, et al., "Formation Mechanism, Geometric Stability and Catalytic Activity of a Single Iron Atom Supported on N-Doped Graphene," *Chemphyschem* 20, no. 19 (2019): 2506.
43. Y. Zeng, E. Almatrafi, W. Xia, et al., "Nitrogen-Doped Carbon-based Single-Atom Fe Catalysts: Synthesis, Properties, and Applications in Advanced Oxidation Processes," *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* 475 (2023): 214874.
44. K. Sun, H. Shan, H. Neumann, G. P. Lu, and M. Beller, "Efficient Iron Single-Atom Catalysts for Selective Ammoxidation of Alcohols to Nitriles," *Nature Communications* 13, no. 1 (2022): 1848.
45. A. M. Agour, E. Elkersh, G. E. Khedr, H. G. El-Aqapa, and N. K. Allam, "Fe-Single-Atom Catalysts on Nitrogen-Doped Carbon Nanosheets for Electrochemical Conversion of Nitrogen to Ammonia," *ACS Applied Nano Materials* 6, no. 17 (2023): 15980.
46. T. Yang, S. Fan, Y. Li, and Q. Zhou, "Fe-N/C Single-Atom Catalysts with High Density of Fe-N_x Sites toward Peroxymonosulfate Activation for High-Efficient Oxidation of Bisphenol A: Electron-Transfer Mechanism," *Chemical Engineering Journal* 419 (2021): 129590.
47. X. Cheng, Z. Pan, C. Lei, et al., "A Strongly Coupled 3D Ternary Fe₂O₃@Ni₂P/Ni(PO₃)₂ Hybrid for Enhanced Electrocatalytic Oxygen Evolution at Ultra High Current Densities," *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 7, no. 3 (2019): 965.
48. Y. Li, Y. Kong, Y. Hou, et al., "In Situ Growth of Nitrogen-Doped Carbon-Coated γ -Fe₂O₃ Nanoparticles on Carbon Fabric for Electrochemical N₂ Fixation," *ACS Sustainable Chemistry and Engineering* 7, no. 9 (2019): 8853.
49. X. Yang, J. Cheng, X. Yang, et al., "O-Hetero-Fe-N_{3.6} Active Sites in ZIF-Derived Carbon Nanotubes for the Electrocatalytic Oxygen Evolution Reaction," *Chemical Engineering Journal* 455 (2023): 140694.
50. C. Kim, H. Min, J. Kim, and J. H. Moon, "Boosting Electrochemical Methane Conversion by Oxygen Evolution Reactions on Fe-N-C Single Atom Catalysts," *Energy & Environmental Science* 16, no. 7 (2023): 3158.
51. Z. Ma, S. Liu, N. Tang, et al., "Coexistence of Fe Nanoclusters Boosting Fe Single Atoms to Generate Singlet Oxygen for Efficient Aerobic

Oxidation of Primary Amines to Imines,” *ACS Catalysis* 12, no. 9 (2022): 5595.

52. C. Zhu, Q. Shi, B. Z. Xu, et al., “Hierarchically Porous M–N–C (M = Co and Fe) Single-Atom Electrocatalysts with Robust MN_x Active Moieties Enable Enhanced ORR Performance,” *Advanced Energy Materials* 8, no. 29 (2018): 1801956.

53. X. Luo, X. Wei, H. Wang, et al., “Secondary-Atom-Doping Enables Robust Fe–N–C Single-Atom Catalysts with Enhanced Oxygen Reduction Reaction,” *Nano Micro Letters* 12, no. 1 (2020): 163.

54. S. Baek, S.-H. Yu, S.-K. Park, et al., “A One-Pot Microwave-Assisted Non-Aqueous Sol–Gel Approach to Metal Oxide/Graphene Nanocomposites for Li-ion Batteries,” *RSC Advances* 1, no. 9 (2011): 1687.

55. M. Hu, J. Xu, J. Gao, S. Yang, J. S. Wong, and R. K. Li, “Benzyl Alcohol-based Synthesis of Oxide Nanoparticles: The Perspective of S(N)1 Reaction Mechanism,” *Dalton Transactions* 42, no. 26 (2013): 9777.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Supporting Fig. S1:** Raman spectra of Fe_{NP}@NG. **Supporting Fig. S2:** (a–e) HR-TEM and (f) SAED images of Fe_{NP}@NG. **Supporting Fig. S3:** (a–e) HR-TEM and (f) SAED images of Fe₁@NG. **Supporting Fig. S4:** XPS survey scan: (a) Fe₁@NG, (b) Fe_{NP}@NG. XPS spectra of Fe_{NP}@NG: (c) Fe 2p, (d) N 1s, (e) C 1s. BET surface area and pore size analysis: Nitrogen (N₂) adsorption–desorption isotherms of (f) NG, (g) Fe_{NP}@NG. MP plot: pore diameter of (h) NG, (i) Fe_{NP}@NG. **Supporting Fig. S5:** (a) Reusability study of the Fe₁@NG catalyst for imination reaction. Reaction conditions: 4-Nitrotoluene (1 mmol), benzyl alcohol (8 mmol), Fe₁@NG (10 mg), 3 h and microwave (MW) reactor (Model: CEM SP Discover and power 120 W). Conversion and selectivity were calculated based on nitrobenzene by GC-MS. b) XRD pattern of fresh and reused Fe₁@NG catalyst. (c) XPS spectra of Fe 2p reused of Fe₁@NG catalyst. HR-TEM images (d,e) fresh and (f,g) reused Fe₁@NG catalyst. **Supporting Fig. S6:** GC chromatogram and mass spectra of precursors, reaction intermediates and products. **Supporting Fig. S7:** Mass spectra of different imine products. **Supporting Table S1:** XPS deconvolution results of N 1s and C 1s of Fe_{NP}@NG and Fe₁@NG. **Supporting Table S2:** The EXAFS fitting of Fe₁@NG. **Supporting Table S3:** The surface textual properties of NG, Fe_{NP}@NG and Fe₁@NG. **Supporting Table S4:** Control experiments for the reductive coupling of 4-nitrophenol and benzyl alcohol over Fe₁@NG catalyst under microwave irradiation.^a **Supporting Table S5:** Comparison of Fe₁@NG single-atom catalyst with previously reported heterogenous catalyst for reductive coupling reactions.